

SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP: ESSENCE AND IMPORTANCE

S.N.Xashimova, Z.M.Mamatmo'minova

Toshkent state technical university

doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11300946

Abstract: The article describes the essence of social entrepreneurship, its importance, as well as issues related to the development of social entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan.

Key words: social entrepreneurship, needy stratum, traditional business, social problems, privilege, social institutions.

In the middle of the twentieth century, the concept of "social business" began to be used in capitalist countries. Its essence lies in the fact that the business does not just make a profit, but does useful work for society. People in this field are not motivated by the desire to make a profit, but by the desire to solve some global problems of humanity, for example, water shortage or environmental pollution. The idea was to force entrepreneurs to look differently at areas that could generate income.

Today, in many countries of the world, more and more entrepreneurs are working at the intersection of philanthropy and commerce, innovation and traditional business practices to solve social problems. Nevertheless, the legal aspects of the development of the phenomenon of "social entrepreneurship" are still in their initial stages.

In our country, development of social entrepreneurship and social protection of the population is one of our most important tasks.

It has been shown that development of production, increase of business entities in increasing the income of the population, especially prevention of a sharp decrease in the income of the low-income and unemployed segments of the population is a very important and urgent task.

A lot of attention is paid to the social and material support of the population, the needy stratum, and their problem cannot be completely solved by providing material aid and money for financial aid included in the list of those in need of assistance.

Today, it is important to implement new approaches to solving socially important problems, to introduce methods widely used in international experience. Therefore, it is important to find a solution to this problem only through the development of social entrepreneurship, which is widely entering our lives today. Social entrepreneurship is a type of entrepreneurship aimed at solving social problems of society. Simply put, this is a business with a social purpose, in which the profits are not directed to increase the income of the owners of the enterprise. The work of such enterprises mainly involves socially unstable persons or persons with disabilities.

In accordance with the current legislation, tax and other benefits are established for enterprises that produce products and equipment for people with disabilities. However, the legal concept of "social entrepreneurship" and the mechanisms of legal regulation of

relations related to social entrepreneurship are not clearly defined in the current legislation.

When studying the legislation of the USA, Great Britain, Poland, Belgium, Italy and other countries regarding social entrepreneurship, as a result of the establishment of this entrepreneurial activity, as well as providing employment to the socially vulnerable sections of the population, the production of social goods and social services it can be seen that a high result has been achieved in terms of rendering.

Based on their social importance, persons with disabilities of groups I and II, disabled children, single persons with dependent children under the age of 16 or with disabilities, and "Kindness" as persons belonging to the socially needy categories of the population graduates of their houses under the age of 30 and persons released from prisons are being determined.

Creating and developing a social entrepreneurship institute in our country is one of the most effective ways to solve social problems.

State support for social entrepreneurship in foreign countries is carried out in the following forms:

- providing benefits and preferences;
- subsidizing social project costs;
- placement of the state social order;
- financial support;
- training, retraining and upgrading the skills of social enterprise employees;
- providing advice, methodical assistance and informational support.

The development of social entrepreneurship can solve the following problems:

- formation of civilized and competitive market relations that help to meet the needs of society;
- improving the quality of products, work and services, expanding their types;
- to increase the level of service;
- bringing product production closer to specific consumers;
- reducing the level of unemployment and creating additional jobs;
- attracting certain categories of citizens to work (pensioners, disabled, students, etc.);
- to support the reconstruction of the economy;
- formation of the social layer of owners, entrepreneurs;
- use of local raw materials from large production waste;
- stimulation of large-scale production by creating tools and equipment, production of components, service and auxiliary industries;
- activation of scientific and technical development;
- freeing the economic sector from unprofitable and low-profit enterprises by buying or leasing them.

Social entrepreneurship, which strives to meet consumer demands, gives mobility, flexibility and agility to the economy.

The use of the resource of self-organization by socially oriented business can significantly reduce the costs of providing social services compared to commercial organizations and increase the standard of living of the population by meeting the needs of citizens for services not provided by the existing social infrastructure.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the reduction of economic growth rates in the world and its socio-economic consequences are prevented by the governments of developed and developing countries, giving priority to the development of effective measures to create the legal basis of social entrepreneurship.

In the conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, development of normative frameworks, including subsidies for them, providing for a system of full support by the state for the creation and development of a social entrepreneurship institute. providing benefits and preferences, using the experience of the USA, Great Britain, Poland, Belgium, Italy and other countries is important.

References

1. Law No. 376 of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Social Partnership". Chapter II, Article 5
2. <https://oldparliament.gov.uz/uz/laws/discussed/33501/>
3. <https://spravochnick.ru/sociologiya/>